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Migration Impact on Remittances Special Focus on Gulf Countries: A Case Study of Pakistan

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Abstract : This article is a case study of Pakistan's labor migration to the Gulf countries from 2006 to 2018. The outflow, patterns and trends of the Pakistani labor force in the Gulf countries and their current structure and the categories of migrants' labor workers like as skilled and unskilled are discussed. It also provides the summary of reasons for labor migration from Pakistan to the Gulf States, such as unemployment, low salaries and poverty. Labor migration in the Gulf States refers to the flow of population in the region mainly for employment purposes. Pakistan has been actively involved in dispatching workers to the Gulf region and the rest of the world. In terms of cash remittances received, Pakistan is the world's leading labor sending country. Labor exports reduce unemployment; increase wages, and remittances sent to the country, improve the international balance of payments, reduce poverty, improve health, educational outcomes, promote economic development, and reduce the negative impact of mountain society. We have studied who, why and how many people allocate and move for labor from Pakistan to Gulf region and the factors involved in labor migration along with its effects. We have found Saudi Arabia and UAE are highly generated remittances countries in the Gulf region and about (44.18%) and (35.44%) respectively.

Keywords : Labor Migration, Remittances, Gulf Region, Unemployment, Skilled & Non-skilled

1. Introduction

Migration is a form of geographic or spatial mobility involving a change of usual residence between clearly defined geographic units (Edmonston & Michalowski, 2004).

Migration is intertwined with geopolitics, trade and cultural exchange, and provides opportunities for States, businesses and communities to benefit enormously. International migration is a complex phenomenon that touches on a multiplicity of economic, social and security aspects affecting our daily lives in an increasingly interconnected world (McAuliffe & Ruhs, 2017).

The United Nations Recommendations on Statistics of International Migration defines an international migrant as any person who has changed his or her country of usual residence, distinguishing between “short-term migrants” (those who have changed their country of usual residence for at least three months, but less than one year) and “long-term migrants” (those who have done so for at least one year) (DESA, 1998).

Obviously, migration has both positive and negative impact on the migrants, their families, and also the sending and receiving countries. The world is facing huge challenges of property development and the billions of individual’s still flat ligneous financial condition and are empty a lifetime of pleasure. Particularly, youth unemployment may be a major concern. Like other less developed countries, Pakistan is facing with issues of large financial condition and speedy increase in its labor migration (Kamrava & Babar, 2012).

With such a large working age population in Pakistan, associate increasing varieties of staff have stimulated migration to different countries for employment. Pakistan annually sends abroad the second largest grouping staff in south Asia, primarily to the Gulf regions. Pakistan depends heavily on labor migration as Associate Avenue for reducing each state and financial condition. Migration is recognized as a central measurement of globalization, touching most countries around the world as points of origin, shipment or purpose for migrants.

Since the mid years of 1970, once dramatically rising oil costs light producing to associate economic boom within the oil rich countries of the Gulf region, large scale temporary and circular foreign employee migration has accommodated the associated labor desires. Pakistani staff is an oversized presence in this movement moreover as within the flow to different new opportunities within the world, notably the United Kingdom (UK), North America (US) and Europe (EU).

These migrant population have contributed heavily to Pakistan’s development through remittances, their gaining of latest and updated data and skills and different social assets they

non heritable whereas operating abroad. Yet, there's very little understanding of their contribution to the event of their communities in Pakistan more over as their purpose countries. And despite their valuable contributions, they are subjected to in the deepness abuse and management throughout the achievement and employment stages of their migration journey.

Historically, migration was seen as a curve with negative suggestions for development. Today, there's a growing detection that migration and migrants will improve a country's development. One among the factors that contributed to the current amendment in thinking is that the growing gratitude of the importance of allowances.”

In this study, we have discussed and enlightened the following aspects regarding migration:

- ❖ Recognized the outflow, patterns and trends.
- ❖ Expressed the categories of migrants' workers.
- ❖ Highlighted the causes and reasons of labor migration.
- ❖ Discussed the remittances received for different purposes.

Further, the structure of the paper is as follows: In Section 2, we present a short overview of related works and research on the particular subject; in Section 3, we define related methods used; in Section 4, we interpret the results and findings of various aspects; in Section 5, we leave the reader with concluding thoughts.

2. Literature Reviews

According to the records of Overseas Employment Corporation (OEC) and Bureau of Emigration and Overseas Employment (BEOE), more than 8.7 million Pakistani workers have been employed abroad since the 1970s. Most of them are registered with BEOE. In the past 50 years, only 139,354 Pakistani workers have used OEC services. According to the BEOE record, the annual resettlement rate of Pakistanis increased from 143,329 in 2005 to 431,842 in 2008. After the decline in the next two years, 458,229 migrant workers were reached in 2011, after reaching 639,601 workers in 2012 and 753,841 workers in 2014. In the first ten months of 2015, a total of 774,795 migrant workers left Pakistan. It is estimated that as of the end of December 2015, the figure has exceeded 800,000, setting a new record (Development, 2015).

(McAuliffe & Ruhs, 2017) expressed that the Kuwait Oil Company listed 1,221 Pakistani employees on a payroll of about Rs.7,000; while ARAMCO indicated 1,042 Pakistani employees on a payroll of about Rs.17,000.

In the early 1970s, the migration to the Gulf region grabbed off. By the early 1980s, about 2 million Pakistanis had migrated there. By the early 1980s, as many as 2 million Pakistanis were estimated to have immigrated to this oil-rich region. The main destinations are Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and the United Arab Emirates, but there are also large numbers of immigrants from other countries, including Iran, Iraq, Qatar, Bahrain, and Oman("Reports & Statistics," 2016).

According to the 1998 census, about 10 million people, or 8% of Pakistan's population, are made up of domestic or international immigrants(Gazdar, 2003).In recent years, the number of immigrants entering the Organization for Economic Corporation and Development (OECD) countries has been increasing, but the growth rate is slower than the pre-crisis level in 2008. In 2011, the total numbers of permanent immigrants in OECD countries were higher than in 2010 and less than 4 million(*Pakistan Economic Survey; 2016-17*, 2017).

Pakistan is one of the top 10 immigrant countries in the world. Pakistani immigrants are mainly focused in Saudi Arabia, and United Arab Emirates (UAE). Overall, these two countries accounted for 68%, and 73% of the total number of immigrants. Although Saudi Arabia's share has recently declined after peaking (37%) in 1990, the UAE's share has remained more or less consistent during this period, slightly above 20%("Reports & Statistics," 2016).

Since 1971, more than 8 million Pakistanis have gone abroad to work. Pakistani migrant workers currently travel to more than 50 destination countries, and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries are the most common choice for Pakistani migrant's workers. During 2008-16, about 97% of Pakistani immigrants workers have traveled to the GCC countries(*Pakistan Economic Survey; 2016-17*, 2017).Almost half live in the Gulf countries, with 1.1 million living and working in Saudi Arabia and 500,000 living and working in the UAE(Hunzai, 2010).

Migrant's workers from Pakistan to the oil-exporting countries of the Middle East are an important part of the movement and presently include at least 3 million foreigners(Amjad & Arif, 2014).

The scale of immigration from Pakistan to the Middle East shows that it has at least some impact on Pakistan's domestic labor market. It is estimated that more than 5% of the country's approximately 24 million labor force work overseas, and the proportion of certain occupations is much higher(Gazdar, 2003).

Pakistani community in Bahrain, according to sources quoted by Addleton, numbered 2,200; by 1965 it had climbed to almost 4000, and by 1971 it stood at 5,400. As early as 1957, almost half of the population in Kuwait comprised non-nationals, and of them a small number came from Pakistan. In 1958, Pakistan was already the single most important source of non-Arab expatriate labor in Kuwait Oil Company and trailed only Americans among those working for ARMACO in Saudi Arabia, representing about nineteen percent of the workforce in the former and six percent in the latter(Choucri, 1986).

Between 1971 and 2015, BEOE handled the placement of 8.365 million Pakistani workers in the overseas labor market. 96% of them are employed in GCC countries, including Saudi Arabia (50%) and the UAE (33%). Oman is the destination country for about 8% of Pakistani workers who have gone abroad through BEOE. Bahrain, Kuwait and Qatar have relatively small shares, at 1.7%, 2.2% and 1.4% respectively. The current stock of Pakistanis in the Middle East is estimated at about 3 million, which indicates that more than 5 million workers have returned to their homes in the past four decades, but repeated immigration cannot be ruled out("Pakistan Economic Survey 2016-17,").

Pakistan is one of the most populous countries in the world, which is estimated to mean that about 3.2% of the population of 169.7 million people in 2009 lived abroad. Saudi Arabia and the UK are the main countries for Pakistani immigrants, with each country accounting for 22% of the total, followed by the United States (16%), the UAE (13%) and Canada (5%)(Azam, 2013).

Most Pakistanis immigrate to Saudi Arabia (61%), followed by the UAE (28%); 9% to other Islamic countries, and only 1.5% to non-Muslim countries in Europe and Asia. Due to demand, the number of immigrants in Pakistan has increased significantly, from 78,093 in 1991 to 184,274 in 2006(Arif & Ishaq, 2015). The largest increase occurred in 2008 and 2009, when labor migration was 431,842 and 404,568 respectively; in 2007, the figure was only 287,707. In fact, 2008 was the first year in the history of labor migration in Pakistan, and the annual flow exceeded the 300,000 mark. In 2010, the World Bank ranked 7th among the countries with the most immigrants, and ranked 13th among the countries with the most immigrants (*Labour Migration from Pakistan: 2015 Status Report*, 2015).

According to the national report for the period 2006-2010, the GCC countries have an estimated stock of 4.5 million Indians, 2.7 million Indonesians, 2.1 million Pakistanis, 2.4 million Filipinos and 2.7 million Sri Lankans, while the recent Bangladesh inventory estimates the number cannot be found(Hasan & Raza, 2009).

2.1 Who Migrate?

Production workers account for 83% of the immigrant labor force, and more than half of them are unskilled. The remaining 17% of immigrants are mostly the titles of professional workers, merchants or salespeople, service staff and civilian staff. According to reports, about 12% of unskilled workers immigrating to the Middle East are agricultural laborers. Another 88% of unskilled labor includes ordinary workers and loaders. Among skilled labor, prominent immigrant occupations are drivers, masons, electricians, carpenters and tailors, accounting for 28% of the immigrant labor force. Other skills to move to the Middle East include machine operators, mechanics, welders, steel fixtures, preservatives, and more (Taylor, 1999).

In this study, due to the temporary nature of the former, the skill composition of Middle Eastern workers is more important than that of workers in other parts of the world. According to the BEOE data, the skills of Pakistani workers in the Middle East during the period 1981-2013 are Professional and semi-professional categories include professionals with a high level of education, such as doctors, engineers and teachers. Work requiring formal or informal training is included in the “skilled” and “semi-skilled” categories, including technicians, electricians, drivers, masons, carpenters, cooks, tailors, etc. Workers and agricultural workers are included in the “unskilled” category (G M Arif & Amjad, 2014).

2.2 Causes and Reasons

There are also political connections, such as the political links between the Sultanate of Oman and Baluchistan in the coastal areas of Pakistan, which have led to the migration from these areas to Oman. Initially, as the Gulf economy began investing in physical infrastructure, there was a great demand for skilled and unskilled construction workers. As these economies grow, they also need a large number of workers with different skills, especially transportation; trade, social infrastructure and other services, and even provide private and public safety. One of the main channels of this flow is the pilgrimage route. The Saudi Arabian government previously issued a pilgrimage visa (Umra visa) to Pakistani Muslims, and many workers arrived in the country with these visas. Then, the workers exceeded their visa period and started trading in low-income jobs or services (Gazdar, 2003).

There are two factors that have caused Asians to enter the Middle East labor market on a large scale. First, the demand for migrant workers exceeds the ability of Arab countries to provide these needs. Second, South Asian workers voluntarily accept jobs and wages that Arab workers resist (Choucri, 1986a).

Labor migration is a global phenomenon that provides reciprocal benefits to the economies of countries that rely on external sources of labor and the economies of countries that send citizens to work overseas. Host countries, such as the GCC, require migrant workers to both stimulate and sustain economic growth. The sending country relies on labor migration as a safety valve against the rise in domestic unemployment and relies on workers to send back domestic financial remittances (Kamrava & Babar, 2012).

The promotion of “push” and “pull” phenomena exists throughout the world. In search of a better life, people were driven out of their health and home to other countries. Unemployed and poor life forced them to leave their homes and experienced endless hardships when they were looking for “green pastures” in developed countries. Both skilled and unskilled labors are transferred to developed countries(Prof. Dr. Rashid Khan, Sareer Khan, & Yorid Ehsan Zia, 2012).

There are several periods in which the labor force migrated from Pakistan to the Gulf. Due to the normal trade and navigation interactions between the coastal Baluchistan and Sindh provinces adjacent to Pakistan, due to the first historical link between South Korea and Saudi Arabia between the Hajj and the Gulf coastal countries. These historical connections were strengthened during the British colonial period. In the first half of the 20th century. It is estimated that around 1970, the number of Pakistani people in the Gulf region was 200,000(I. S. Gilani, 2009).

Labor exports have reduced unemployment; increased wages and remittances sent home have improved the balance of payments and reduced poverty(Aqeel & Aqeel, 2015). The Gulf countries have rich oil wealth and provide unprecedented economic opportunities for Pakistani workers mainly in the construction sector. Therefore, unlike immigrants who flow to developed countries, immigrants to the Gulf region open the door to uneducated young people from Pakistan(Hunzai, 2010).

Motivation for immigrants is the driving factors (poverty, unemployment, low wages, high fertility, lack of basic health and education, discrimination based on race, religion, etc.) and stimulating factors (potentials for raising wages, raising the standard of living), individuals Or career development, family reunion, etc.)(Europe et al., n.d.).

In addition to poverty alleviation, immigrants are seen as a mechanism for transferring new skills to labor-contributing countries, and migrant workers bring new knowledge and skills back to the country. The main drivers are the lack of employment and employment opportunities in the domestic labor market and the security situation in the country(GIZ &

ILO, 2016). The first immigrants from the modern economic order of the Arab world were locals, and the oil companies' own labor needs were limited (Abu-Lughod, 2005).

On the other hand, poverty and lack of decent work have become reasons for leaving the country, which is considered economic immigration. People in developing countries have a global trend of turning to developed countries for a more comfortable life (A.A.I.N. Wickramasinghe & Wijitapure Wimalaratana, 2016).

Dubai and Qatar have recently become major recipients of foreign workers due to the growth of their construction industry. The high demand for semi-labor and unskilled labor shapes the gender and age composition of the non-national population (Al-Najjar, 2006).

The main reason why Pakistan encourages international migration is that it reduces unemployment (Hunzai, 2010). Pakistan relies heavily on labor migration as a way to reduce unemployment and poverty. In the five years from 2011 to 2015, more than 3 million people left the country to work in foreign countries (Labour migration from Pakistan: 2015 status report).

The volume and dynamics of these flows are first driven by variations in oil prices and the resulting demand for foreign workers who are employed in the oil economy and infrastructure development (Chowdhury, 2018).

2.3 Government Policies for Overseas Pakistani Labor

The Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper (PRSP) is the main policy document of the Pakistani government on poverty. The policy directions are as follows: macroeconomic stability and economic growth reforms; social sector goals based on expenditures, temporary and final outcomes; safety nets for specific vulnerable groups; and specific programs such as microfinance schemes and public works projects for income and job creation (Gazdar, 2003).

Local immigration laws often strengthen short-lived ideas: work permits are required, and citizenship in Arab countries is almost impossible to obtain. The law for accompanying family members also limits the possibility of long-term expatriates and second-generation immigrants. For example, workers in Saudi Arabia can only bring their families with university education, while in Kuwait, if workers want to be accompanied by their families, a minimum wage is required. The government also maintains a policy aimed at increasing the value of remittances returned to Pakistan in the form of goods or capital goods. Although the personal baggage and gift plan is still limited, it has fewer restrictions than in the past, and import prices on certain items have been reduced (J. Addleton, 1984).

Immigration regulations in Pakistan not only punish illegal immigrants, but also impose fines on migrant workers who violate the terms of an agreement with foreign employers by deserting employment (BEOE 2012). The Pakistani government has taken many measures to control and regulate the country's labor recruitment process. In the 1970s, when Chinese labor migration began on a large scale, the three organizations, the National Human Resources Committee, the Seafarers' Welfare Bureau and the Immigration Protection Bureau merged into the Immigration Service and the BEOE. BEOE as a regulator/authority controls, manages, promotes and supervises the immigration process. (Ghulam Mohammad Arif & Ishaq, 2017).

Pakistan has developed all the necessary institutional arrangements and legislation for the recruitment and placement of labor and overseas labor markets. The Pakistani government actively promotes labor migration and provides incentives to facilitate the flow of migrant remittances. However, the policy system followed by the Pakistani government does not reduce poverty or improve the livelihood of immigrants, which is one of its hidden goals. (Ghulam Mohammad Arif & Ishaq, 2017).

The policy considers the lack of information about the challenges of returning immigrants, immigration gender apartheid, job opportunities, intentional immigration choices or descriptions, and adequate information on immigration health. It also points to the collection, collation and analysis of enhanced orientation/newsletters for future immigrants and timely response to information gaps in emergency situations, development programs, projects and immigration policies. In addition, it identifies the role of other stakeholders, especially the migrant workers association, in guiding future immigration and advocating for their rights (Maqsood Ahmad Jan, 2010).

2.4 Remittances Received from Overseas Pakistani

In 2016, 840,000 laborers flooded to different countries, especially Saudi Arabia and the Middle East, which not only contributed to the economy of the host country through their services, but also remitted money to the country (Hunzai, 2010).

Immigrants in the Gulf region include a large number of uneducated people from rural areas; their remittances directly affect poverty. From the perspective of macroeconomic management, Gulf migration clearly shows the huge impact of international migration on the domestic economy. Foreign currency remittances from overseas immigrants have become an important independent analysis category for economic managers. Remittances have also become the largest source of foreign exchange earnings (Gazdar, 2003).

In the early 1980s, this flow was equivalent to 10% of Gross National Product (GNP). At present, the amount of remittances is 2.4 billion US dollars, accounting for 4% of the gross national product(Gazdar, 2003).

In turn, Pakistan has been the recipient of remittances from these workers, including many families who are now permanently settled abroad, and who themselves build assets and savings in countries where they still feel deeply connected. In 2012-13, Pakistan received about \$13 billion in wage remittances through formal (bank) channels, which accounted for almost 60% of its total export revenue and more than 5% of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP)(G M Arif & Amjad, 2014).

A bad situation occurred after the 2010 floods, and remittances, which also played an important role in rebuilding the infrastructure, while maintaining livelihoods during and immediately after the floods, which also destroyed crops, washed away roads, shops and destroyed other economic activities and means of livelihood(G M Arif & Amjad, 2014).

Immigrants continue to exile their income, and large amounts of remittances appear in balance-of-payments accounts, and sending countries have begun to rely on these revenues as their main source of foreign exchange(Choucri, 1986b).

Once remittances receive in Pakistan, the use of remittances depends to a large extent on the investment climate of the country as a whole. Initial use may include repayment of old debt or purchase of exposed consumer goods such as televisions or tape players. Housing construction and land purchases have also proven to be welcome investments. Both the government and the private sector have made significant efforts to occupy the housing and construction sectors of the remittance market(J. Addleton, 1984).

In 2016, immigrant remittances from developing countries were approximately \$413 billion. Remittances are an important source of household income, improving the livelihoods of families and communities by investing in education, health, sanitation, housing and infrastructure(UN, 2017).

Due to the large number of workers in Saudi Arabia and the UAE, most of the remittances in 2014-15 came from two countries: Saudi Arabia 30.1%, UAE 22.6%, of which 11.6% came from other GCCcountries in the UAE(Labour migration from Pakistan: 2015 status report).

The relationship between real GDP growth and worker remittances is part of real GDP growth. It also shows that workers' remittances play an important role in Pakistan's real GDP growth. Therefore, quantitative evidence shows that real GDP growth is positively related to

workers' remittances, and remittances are the third largest source of capital for Pakistan's economic growth (Hasan & Raza, 2009).

Pakistan is at 11th number in stretch of receiving remittances. For many years, Pakistan has been one of the main remittances for receiving countries, with remittances accounting for 10% of GDP. Remittances often exceed public and private foreign capital inflows. This helps to recompense for the country's long-term current account deficit, expand the economy, and contribute to the income of local families. Estimates for overseas Pakistanis range from an official 4 million to a narrative of 500 to 6 million to a more hypothetical 800 to 10 million. The main focus of the expatriates is in Saudi Arabia (1.1 million) and the UAE (500,000) (Azam, 2013, Makhoulouf & Mughal, 2010).

3. Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework

There is ample evidence that immigrant social networks are very active in the Middle East to promote immigration from their relatives and friends. As Lucas (2005) described, Azam researchers who migrated from two parts of Pakistan to these countries found that about 40% to 50% of immigrants were resettled through friends and relatives. Another survey conducted by (Shah 1998) in South Asian men in Kuwait validated the findings and reported that among technical and non-skilled workers in Pakistan, friends and relatives provided 48% and 63% of the help for these workers (Aqeel & Aqeel, 2015).

Some surveys on immigration from Pakistan also provide evidence of social networks to help future immigrants obtain visas and jobs. A review of the theoretical literature points to the various dynamics of international migration. The migration process is based on factors determining both the supply and demand sides, including economic, socio political and demographic factors. Network theory uses a dynamic approach and considers both revenue/utility maximization and cost minimization. According to network theory, in order to maximize its effectiveness, potential immigrants are more willing to live with friends and relatives who have migrated before. These established networks of immigrants help reduce the economic and uneconomic costs of potential immigrants (Aqeel & Aqeel, 2015).

The registration data of BEOE over the past 40 years shows that half of Pakistani workers go abroad, while the remaining half get employment through direct contact with overseas employers. Social networks in the form of friends/relatives who have worked in the GCC countries and direct contact between employers and potential immigrants have played an important role in obtaining employment visas without the involvement of recruitment

agencies. The size and pattern of irregular migration may vary depending on the method of recruiting workers; however, the data for this association cannot be checked (Ghulam Mohammad Arif & Ishaq, 2017).

3.2 Source of Data

Data extracted either from Bureau of Emigration and Overseas Pakistani (BEOE), State Bank of Pakistan (SBP), Ministry of Finance, Govt. of Pakistan, Bureau of Statistics Pakistan, World Bank Data and Report 2017 & 2018, Balance of payment Statistics – Database and Browser, International Monetary Fund (IMF), and United Nations Population Division (UNPD).

3.3 Integration and Transformation of Data

Data collected from different sources need to be integrated and transformed. For this objective, **Table 1** illustrates the number of Pakistani labor migrants to GCC countries from 2006 – 2018, and **Table 2**, describes the fiscal year remittances in \$US million received in Pakistan.

Table 1 Year wise labor migration

Years/Countries	Bahrain	Kuwait	Oman	Qatar	Saudi Arabia	UAE	Total
2006	1,630	10,545	12,614	2,247	45,594	100,207	172,837
2007	2,615	14,544	32,474	5,006	84,587	139,405	278,631
2008	5,932	6,250	37,441	10,171	138,283	221,765	419,842
2009	7,087	1,542	34,089	4,061	201,816	140,889	389,484
2010	5,877	153	37,878	3,039	189,888	113,312	350,147
2011	10,641	173	53,525	5,121	222,247	156,353	448,060
2012	10,530	5	69,407	7,320	358,560	182,630	628,452
2013	9,600	229	47,794	8,119	270,502	273,234	609,478
2014	9,226	132	39,793	10,042	312,489	350,522	722,204
2015	9,029	164	47,788	12,741	522,750	326,986	919,458
2016	8,226	770	45,085	9,706	462,598	295,647	822,032
2017	7,919	773	42,362	11,592	143,363	275,436	481,445
2018	5,745	493	27,202	20,993	100,910	208,635	363,978
Total	94,057	35,773	527,452	110,158	3,053,587	2,785,021	6,606,048

Table 2 Fiscal year remittances

Years/Countries	Bahrain	Kuwait	Oman	Qatar	Saudi Arabia	UAE	Total
FY-2006	100.57	246.75	130.45	118.69	750.44	716.3	2,063.2
FY-2007	136.28	288.71	161.69	170.65	1,023.56	866.49	2,647.38
FY-2008	140.51	384.58	224.94	233.36	1,251.32	1,090.3	3,325.01
FY-2009	153.27	432.05	277.82	339.51	1,559.56	1,688.59	4,450.80
FY-2010	151.35	445.09	287.27	354.15	1,917.66	2,038.52	5,194.04

FY-2011	167.29	495.19	337.59	306.11	2,670.07	2,597.74	6,573.99
FY-2012	210.95	582.57	382.66	318.82	3,687.00	2,848.86	8,030.86
FY-2013	282.83	619	384.8	321.25	4,104.73	2,750.17	8,462.78
FY-2014	318.84	681.43	530.52	329.24	4,729.43	3,109.52	9,698.98
FY-2015	388.99	748.12	685.71	350.21	5,630.43	4,231.75	12,035.20
FY-2016	448.44	773.97	819.44	380.86	5,968.25	4,365.29	12,756.30
FY-2017	396.39	763.8	760.89	404.4	5,469.81	4,328.15	12,123.40
FY-2018	355.67	774.22	657.33	371.09	4,858.78	4,358.98	11,376.10
Total	3,251.38	7,235.48	5,641.11	3,998.34	4,3621.00	34,990.70	98,738.04

FY: Fiscal Year

3.4 Statistical Quantitative Analysis

In order to discover the significance of variables related to labor migration and remittances for the fiscal years as shown in **Table 3**, and **Table 4**. As correlation matrix shows the relationship amongst the GCC countries and fiscal years from 2006 – 2018.

Table 3 Correlation matrix for country wise labor migrants

	<i>Bahrain</i>	<i>Kuwait</i>	<i>Oman</i>	<i>Qatar</i>	<i>Saudi Arabia</i>	<i>UAE</i>
Bahrain	1					
Kuwait	-0.83	1				
Oman	0.86	-0.57	1			
Qatar	0.21	-0.36	0.04	1		
Saudi Arabia	0.70	-0.57	0.65	0.17	1	
UAE	0.55	-0.47	0.33	0.59	0.65	1

Table 4 Correlation matrix for remittances

	<i>Bahrain</i>	<i>Kuwait</i>	<i>Oman</i>	<i>Qatar</i>	<i>Saudi Arabia</i>	<i>UAE</i>
Bahrain	1					
Kuwait	0.95	1				
Oman	0.98	0.96	1			
Qatar	0.72	0.85	0.79	1		
Saudi Arabia	0.97	0.98	0.96	0.77	1	
UAE	0.94	0.98	0.97	0.84	0.97	1

Correlation in **Table 3** shows the high correlation between countries which reveals that the outflow of number of migrants in six countries from Pakistan has the high ratio. Every country has plenty of workers residents for the purpose of various job opportunities. Moreover, **Table 4**, justifies the inflow of remittances to Pakistan from different sources of employment. Detailed list of enormous occupations enlisted in **Table 5**.

4. Results and Findings

Skilled and non-skilled labor migrants are categorized according to their education and experience shown in **Table 5**.

Table 5 List of skilled and non-skilled labor workers

Categories	Occupations
Highly Qualified	Engineer, Doctor, Accountant, Pharmacist, Computer/Analyst
Highly Skilled	Nurse, Teacher, Manager
Skilled	Welder, Secretary/Stenographer, Storekeeper, Clerk/Typist, Forman/Supervisor, Carpenter, Electrician, Plumber, Driver, Technician, Mechanic, Surveyor, Steel Fixer, Designer, Goldsmith
Semi-skilled	Mason, Cook, Waiter/Bearer, Painter, Operator, Tailor, Fitter, Rigger, Salesman, Draftsman, Blacksmith, Photographer, Artist, Cable Jointer
Non-skilled	Laborer, Agriculture Worker

Source: From Pakistan to the Gulf Region: An analysis of links between labor markets, skills and the migration cycle (International Labor Migration:2016) (Data: Bureau of Emigration; Pakistan).

Fig. 1 illustrates the year wise skilled and non-skilled number of migrant workers working in various professions. Further **Table 6**, demonstrates the descriptive statistics for year 2006 – 2018.

Figure 1 Migrant workers to GCC countries

Table 6 Descriptive statistics of migrant workers

Descriptive Statistics	Bahrain	Kuwait	Oman	Qatar	Saudi Arabia	UAE
Mean	7235.15	2751.77	40573.23	8473.69	234891.31	214232.38
S.E.	781.3037	1309.0165	3766.1769	1396.0281	40403.5753	23169.6027
Median	7919	493	39793	8119	201816	208635
S.D.	2817.0307	4719.7262	13579.1440	5033.4508	145677.1625	83539.1907

Sample Var	7935662	22275816	184393152	25335627	21221835668	6978796384
Kurtosis	-0.0632	2.6062	1.6464	2.0948	-0.2211	-1.3170
Skewness	-0.7899	1.8925	0.0744	1.1677	0.7544	0.2348
Range	9011	14539	56793	18746	477156	250315
Min	1630	5	12614	2247	45594	100207
Max	10641	14544	69407	20993	522750	350522
Sum	94057	35773	527452	110158	3053587	2785021

S.E.: Standard Error, S.D.: Standard Deviation, Sample Var: Sample Variance

Further, Fig. 2, Pie chart explains the percentage value of labor migrants to all the six countries mentioned in this study which shows Saudi Arabia (46%) and UAE (42%) respectively as both have highest frequency of migrants (skilled and non-skilled) which is a good sign to compare the remittances received as both countries have “high income” status as per the World Bank metadata country file. While others have Bahrain (1.4%), Kuwait (0.54%), Oman (8%), and Qatar (1.67%) respectively.

Figure 2 Skilled & non-skilled migrants

As per the remittances is concerned, Fig 3, illustrates the annual remittance received from the high-income status countries of GCC.

Figure 3 Annual remittances to Pakistan

Table 7, designates the descriptive statistics of remittances which informs the basics of statistics about how data are transformed according to mean and standard deviation.

Table 7 Descriptive statistics of remittances

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>	<i>Bahrain</i>	<i>Kuwait</i>	<i>Oman</i>	<i>Qatar</i>	<i>Saudi Arabia</i>	<i>UAE</i>
Mean	250.11	556.58	433.93	307.56	3355.46	2691.59
S.E.	33.1869	52.1002	64.4626	23.2745	529.3034	376.1556
Median	210.95	582.57	382.66	329.24	3687	2750.17
S.D.	119.6571	187.8500	232.4231	83.9173	1908.4307	1356.2485
Sample Var	14317.8172	35287.6211	54020.4918	7042.1166	3642107.6736	1839409.8594
Kurtosis	-1.5265	-1.3171	-1.2271	1.0682	-1.7186	-1.3805
Skewness	0.3744	-0.2805	0.4306	-1.3215	-0.0461	-0.0688
Range	347.87	527.47	688.99	285.71	5217.81	3648.99
Min	100.57	246.75	130.45	118.69	750.44	716.3
Max	448.44	774.22	819.44	404.4	5968.25	4365.29
Sum	3251.3781	7235.4824	5641.1102	3998.3380	43621.0434	34990.6621

S.E.: Standard Error, S.D.: Standard Deviation, Sample Var: Sample Variance

Fig. 4, describes the percentage value of annual remittances sent by Pakistani residents of Gulf countries in the fiscal years 2006 – 2018.

Figure 4 Comparison of remittances

5. Conclusion and Discussion

This research investigates the relationship between labor migrants and remittances associated with both skilled and non-skilled workers for the years of 2006 – 2018. We have found that total of **6,606,048** workers migrated to Gulf countries for work and different prospects. As per the World Bank report, these six countries (GCC) have high income status and people from developing countries urge to move there to generate and earn maximum revenue, and we

have also discussed in literature reviews that due to this earning they used to send remittances to their families, friends, and relatives, etc.

We then highlighted the total of **98,738.04** US million dollars remittances received in Pakistan during the period of 2006 – 2018. We found Saudi Arabia (44.18%) and UAE (35.44%) are highly generated remittances countries in the Gulf region, and others Bahrain (3.29%), Kuwait (7.33%), Oman (5.71%), and Qatar (4.05%) respectively.

Furthermore, Govt. of Pakistan should provide an ample opportunity to both skilled and non-skilled workers and also give encouragement to go abroad to quest the working options relevant to their skills. As more and more people will migrate then the inflow of remittance will increase which will boost the living style, health, education, power of purchasing, and unemployment and poverty will be decreased and also be beneficial for GDP percentage of per capita income of Pakistan.

Moreover, new bilateral contracts must be signed and make productive policies with other high-income countries to promote the working labor to do work, businesses and maintain their residence there, etc.

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